

Compensation Role in Improving Employees' Performance

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Abstract

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The role of compensation is essential for the company and employees because it impacts both parties' performance. This study aims to analyze what factors affect compensation and how compensation affects employee performance, especially in the automotive component industry in West Java. This research is a type of quantitative research where data is collected by sharing questionnaires with 285 employees who work in automotive component companies in the Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia. Data analysis techniques used are descriptive statistics and structural equation modeling (SEM) using Lisrel 8.8 software tools. The results showed that government policies, trade unions, wage levels, and living costs significantly affected compensation while work productivity had no significant effect on compensation but compensation had a significant impact on employee performance.

1. Introduction

Compensation is a complex issue faced by many companies and a sensitive issue for employees. By the employees, compensation is one of the big motivations that can drive performance. However, for many companies, compensation is a cost that must be calculated carefully to maintain the company's financial condition remains healthy. Because of these two different points of view make many companies cannot fully meet employees' compensation requirement including in the automotive components industry. Therefore, the compensation structure given to employees must have a logical and rational basis. The amount of compensation received by employees reflects or a measure of the employee's work value; the small amount of compensation can affect the employee's performance. If the compensation provided is inappropriate, the employee's performance will be reduced (Soekidjo, 2003). The compensation received by employees is often considered inadequate

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and even considered unfair. Therefore, the determination of compensation must be following the needs of employees in the hope of impacting employee performance and will also impact productivity (Fauzi, 2014). Sari (2015) explained that compensation is divided into two types, namely financial compensation and non-financial compensation. The better the standard level of compensation provided by the company; the more productivity will increase employees' work productivity (Sari, 2015). Adequate compensation will lead to satisfaction that can help companies obtain, maintain, and maintain labor productivity.

On the contrary, Wiantara (2015) explained that high productivity could affect the amount of compensation that employees will receive but in contrast to Pasimeni (2018) that in Europe, productivity does not affect the amount of compensation received by employees. The determination of compensation requires synergy and agreement between the government, unions, and employers acceptable to all involved in determining compensation or wages. The role of government policy affects the size of the regional minimum wage (Izzaty & Sari, 2013; Utami, 2017), but on the other hand, Uzoh and Chigozie (2016) suggested that government policy is not always reliable to determine wage levels. Employees always demand compensation improvement; the determination of compensation (Minimum Wage) often demanded by employees is based on the need for a decent life.

In terms of fulfilling compensation, the role of trade unions has a significant influence on compensation and employee welfare (Huang, Jiang, Lie, 2017; Alvita et al., 2014). However, Ibrahim (2016) argues that the role of trade unions has not been maximized in implementing mandated by Law No. 21 of 2000. So far, the direct compensation received by employees at automotive component companies is not sufficient for living expenses. Employee demands related to compensation. Employees' demand for compensation improvements is made by conducting demonstrations so that many employees cannot meet their production targets because they do not work optimally.

The achievement of a compensation structure that is agreed upon by all parties will certainly positively impact the performance of employees. Fauzi (2014) explains that the level of compensation can affect employee performance, as well as studies conducted by Njoroge & Kwasira (2015) and Hameed et al. (2014), which explain that there is a positive and significant impact between compensation on employee performance. Based on this description, this study aims to analyze how the role of government policies, labor unions, productivity, wage levels, and cost of living in influencing compensation and whether compensation can improve employee performance, especially in the automotive component industry in Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia.

Performance is a comparison between the results of work with established standards (Dessler, 2020). The performance also can be interpreted as the result of work both in quality and quantity achieved by a person in carrying out tasks according to the responsibilities (Mangkunegara, 2007). Rivai & Basri (2005) define performance as the result or level of success of a person as a whole during a specific period in carrying out tasks compared to various possibilities, such as work standards, targets or criteria that have been previously agreed upon. Mathis & Jackson (2012) explains that performance is about what employees do or don't do. Hakim (2006) defines performance as the work achieved by an individual who is adjusted to the role or task of the individual in a company at a particular time. Therefore, it can be concluded that performance measures the quantity and quality achieved by a worker in fulfilling the duties and responsibilities assigned to him/ her.

2. Materials and Methods

Sedarmayanti (2004) states that workers receive compensation in return for the efforts or services they provide. Umar (2007) describes compensation as everything received by workers in salaries, wages, incentives, bonuses, premiums, medicines, insurance, and other similar paid

companies. From this definition, it can be concluded that compensation is the number of packages offered by the organization to employees in return for their energy use. Judging from the way it is given, compensation can be either direct compensation or indirect compensation. Direct compensation is management compensation such as wages and salaries or pays for performance, such as incentives and gain sharing.

In addition to wages, salaries, and incentives, workers can be given other incentives in the form of awards or rewards. The difference between incentives and rewards is that incentives are motivating to further improve their performance; in terms of rewards, workers are more passive. For their work performance, superiors give other additional awards to workers (Wibowo, 2016). Simamora (2014) explains that the compensation indicator consists of five items: salary, wages, incentives, allowances, and facilities.

Government policy exists to protect workers or employees from potential arbitrariness by employers so that the government, in this case, has the authority to determine minimum wages, working hours, certain age limits to achieve employee welfare. In this case, the government plays a critical role in determining the Regional Minimum Wage. However, there is a controversy over PP Policy No. 78 of 2015 concerning Wages. As a result, this year, the determination of wages in Indonesia is back in polemic. Under a letter from the Minister of Manpower, the Provincial Minimum Wage (UMP) determination must be determined as of 1 November 2016 simultaneously throughout Indonesia.

Jaenudin (2015) suggests that government policy is the most dominant factor in influencing compensation. Dipoyudo (2005) explains that the government's participation in setting wage standards promotes the workforce; to protect working groups that earn meager wages; to encourage appropriate remuneration; to create calm at work; to promote the improvement of living standards. Based on this description, it can be concluded that government policies have a role to advance the workforce, protect employees from low wages, encourage the creation of fair wages, create work peace, and encourage employee welfare improvements.

Trade unions are organizations formed from and by workers. This organization helps fight for, defend, and protecting the rights and interests of labor workers. The formation of trade unions is in the context of improving the welfare of workers/labor. Employers have the right and freedom to participate in a trade union organization they want. In Indonesia, the freedom to become a member of an organization of the worker's choice, associated with a particular company, business sector, or region.

Based on the general provisions of Article 1 of the 2003 Manpower Law No. 17, a labor union is an organization formed from, by, and for companies both within and outside the company, which is unrestricted, open, independent, democratic, and responsible for the fight for, segregate and protect employees and improve the welfare of workers and their families. Furthermore, following article 102 of the 2003 Manpower Law, in carrying out industrial relations, workers and trade unions have functions following their obligations, maintaining order for production, channeling aspirations directly, developing skills and expertise, and advancing the company.

Based on Law Number 21 of 2000 concerning Trade Unions, the formation of a labor union can be carried out by a minimum of 10 (ten) workers. Every worker has the right to form and become a member of a trade union. Therefore, there may be more than one union in a company. If a dispute occurs between trade unions in one company, it is a form of industrial relations dispute, which can be resolved through the industrial relations court as referred to in Law Number 2 of 2004 concerning Settlement of Industrial Relations Disputes.

Ningsih et al. (2015) argue that trade unions maintain worker relations in the industrial sphere as representatives of workers and management who represent companies. Trade unions play a role

in accommodating the aspirations of workers in fighting for the rights and interests of their members to be heard by the company management. Management plays a role in managing company assets, one of which is human resources through activities carrying out complex functions in work relationships.

Productivity is an effort from the work of employees to achieve organizational goals that have been set. In general, every company always wants to increase its productivity to show that the company is growing. Yuniarsi (2009) argues that work productivity is a concrete result produced by individuals or groups during a particular time in a work process. Sedarmayanti (2004) explains productivity as creating or increasing the effects of goods and services as high as possible by utilizing human resources efficiently. In line with this opinion, Chandra & Prasetya (2015) defines productivity as a comparison between output and input that effectively uses resources in producing goods and services. Therefore, it can conclude that productivity is closely related to work attitudes, skill levels, relations between workers and leaders, productivity management, work efficiency and effectiveness in producing products or services.

Wages are very crucial in the field of employment. If the wage system is not managed professionally, it will often lead to potential disputes between the company and its employees to strike and demonstrations. Abdul (2006) explains that the wage system is a framework for regulating and applying wages. Soedarjadi (2009) revealed that the wage system in Indonesia is generally based on three functions, namely reflecting the rewards for one's work; ensure a decent life for workers and their families; provide incentive money to encourage increased production of labour.

Halim (2001) explains that in determining wages for workers, employers usually pay attention to several things, namely; the time spent, energy, and skills contributed physically, mentally, and socially; see and conduct surveys with similar companies on the wages given to workers who do the same work; providing incentives to workers who are diligent and have extraordinary achievements to increase productivity. Based on the description, it can be concluded that the indicators for wages are the consumer price index, labour force participation rate, regional domestic product and per capita income.

Mankiw (2013) explain that calculating the cost of living is a mechanism to determine how household actors need much economic value to meet their daily needs. The cost of living is closely related to the consumer price index, which is often used to measure a country's inflation rate and consider adjusting salaries, wages, pensions, and other contracts as a consumer price index.

Winters (2009) suggests that the related living costs and wage levels are determined by several factors, one of which is the location or area of work. For example, in big cities, the price of goods and services offered is relatively higher than in small towns or rural areas, so that workers in large cities will need somewhat higher wages. Sturman et al. (2017) explain that living costs have a positive effect on wages but does not apply to workers in top managerial positions. Based on this study, the living cost can be measured through work location, level of consumption, transportation costs and social costs. Based on the empirical evidence that has been described, the research model is as follows.

Figure 1.1
Research Model

Figure 1 shows that there are six (6) hypotheses that will need to be tested, namely:

- H1: The role of government policy affects the determination of compensation
- H2: The role of workers' organizations affects the determination of compensation
- H3: Productivity affects the determination of compensation
- H4: The wage rate affects the determination of compensation
- H5: Cost of living affects the determination of compensation
- H6: Compensation affects employee performance

This research is a type of survey research with quantitative methods. Data collection techniques using a questionnaire. The sample in this study are employees who work in the automotive component industry in West Java, Indonesia. Questionnaires were distributed randomly to 285 employees working in the industry. The data analysis technique used is descriptive statistics and structural equation modelling (SEM), processed using Lisrel 8.8 software.

3. Results and Discussions

Results

The following Table 1 shows that all questionnaire items on each variable of Government Policy, Trade Unions, Employee Productivity, Wage Levels, Cost of Living, Compensation and Employee Performance are valid because all factor loading values are > 0.50 and the t -value > 1.96 .

Table 1. Construct Validity Test

Indicator	Variable	Loading Factor	T Value	Result
GP.1	Government Policy	0.74	14.4	Valid
GP.2		0.83	16.86	Valid
GP.3		0.76	14.83	Valid
GP.4		0.76	14.89	Valid
GP.5		0.82	16.61	Valid
GP.6		0.83	16.9	Valid
GP.7		0.78	15.45	Valid
GP.8		0.82	16.8	Valid
GP.9		0.79	15.67	Valid
TU.1	Trade Union	0.59	10.3	Valid
TU.2		0.6	10.66	Valid
TU.3		0.66	12.03	Valid
TU.4		0.73	13.54	Valid
TU.5		0.74	13.87	Valid
TU.6		0.72	13.29	Valid
TU.7		0.7	12.96	Valid
TU.8		0.76	14.33	Valid
P.1	Productivity	0.7	13.44	Valid
P.2		0.62	11.31	Valid
P.3		0.65	12.02	Valid
P.4		0.69	12.88	Valid
P.5		0.77	14.94	Valid
P.6		0.68	12.73	Valid
P.7		0.78	14.03	Valid
P.8		0.77	14.99	Valid
P.9		0.79	15.52	Valid
P.10		0.74	14.21	Valid
W.1	Wages	0.81	16.29	Valid
W.2		0.74	14.29	Valid
W.3		0.85	13.42	Valid
W.4		0.79	15.52	Valid
W.5		0.83	17.04	Valid
LC.1	Living Cost	0.71	13.49	Valid
LC.2		0.8	15.95	Valid
LC.3		0.79	15.63	Valid

Indicator	Variable	Loading Factor	T Value	Result
LC.4	Compensation	0.78	13.94	Valid
LC.5		0.8	15.79	Valid
C.1		0.66	10.19	Valid
C.2		0.59	9.14	Valid
C.3		0.64	9.8	Valid
C.4		0.64	9.73	Valid
C.5		0.64	9.79	Valid
C.6		0.71	10.63	Valid
C.7		0.66	10.05	Valid
C.8		0.63	9.57	Valid
C.9	Employee Performance	0.63	9.63	Valid
C.10		0.62	9.54	Valid
EP.1		0.74	14.16	Valid
EP.2		0.72	12.06	Valid
EP.3		0.84	14.21	Valid
EP.4		0.89	15.08	Valid
EP.5	Employee Performance	0.68	11.37	Valid
EP.6		0.64	10.6	Valid

Moreover, the following table 2 shows that P-Values, NCP Interval, RMSEA, ECVI, NFI, NNFI, CFI, IFI, RFI, CN, SRMR, GFI and AGFI meet the goodness of fit criteria, namely from 15 GOF test criteria using 4-5 GOF criteria. They are considered sufficient to meet the feasibility of a model (Hair et al. in Haryono, 2017). Although the probability is not significant, it is sufficient to meet the requirements of the fittest.

Table 2. Goodness of Fit of Model Testing

Goodness of Fit Measure	(Cut off Value)	Result	Conclusion
Chi Square (X^2)	Small value	4773.25	Marginal Fit
P-Values	$P \geq 0,05$	0.00	
NCP Interval	Small value	3464.25	Good Fit
RMSEA	Niche interval	3256.76 ; 3679.17	
ECVI	$\leq 0,08$	0.09	Marginal Fit
NFI	Small value	$M^* = 17.67$	
NNFI		$S^* = 10.08$	
CFI		$I^* = 148.00$	
NFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.91	Good Fit
NNFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.94	Good Fit
CFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.94	Good Fit

IFI	≥ 0,90	0.94	Good Fit
RFI	≥ 0,90	0.91	Good Fit
CN	≥ 200	110.53	Not Fit
SRMR	≥ 0,05	0.091	Good Fit
GFI	Close to 1	0.58	Marginal Fit
AGFI	Close to 1	0.56	Marginal Fit

Figure 2. Structural Model (T Values)

Next, the above figure 2 shows 5 (five) significant path coefficients and 1 (one) insignificant path.

According to Wijayanto (2008) a large t-value with absolute value > 1.96 means that the path coefficient is significant.

Table 3. Hypotheses Test

Code	Hypothesis	T-Value	Decision
H ₁	Government policy has a significant impact on compensation	6.45	Accepted
H ₂	Trade union has a significant impact on compensation	2.52	Accepted
H ₃	Productivity has a significant impact on compensation	0.69	Rejected
H ₄	Wages has a significant impact on compensation	2.88	Accepted
H ₅	Living cost has a significant impact on compensation	3.01	Accepted
H ₆	Compensation has a significant impact on employee performance	6.59	Accepted

Discussions

A. Government policy has a significant impact on compensation

Table 3 shows the T-value is $6.45 > 1.96$, which means that the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. The statistical test results show that government policy has a significant effect on compensation determination. It can be concluded that every change in government policy will cause a significant change in the determination of compensation. It can be concluded that every change in government policy will cause a significant change in the determination of compensation. It means that when the Government Policy changes, it causes a significant change to the Compensation policy. In Indonesia, government policy is very dominant in determining compensation, straightforward compensation. Government policy regulates the relationship between employers and workers, where government policy largely determines the size of the standard of compensation in a company, both government and private companies.

B. Trade union has a significant impact on compensation

Table 3 shows the T-value is $2.52 > 1.96$, which means that the alternative hypothesis (H2) is accepted. The statistical test results show that trade union has a significant effect on compensation. It can be concluded that the union can carry out good negotiations with the company, thus causing a significant change in compensation. It can be concluded that the union can carry out good negotiations with the company, thus causing a significant change in compensation. When the union can carry out good negotiations with the company, it causes a significant change in compensation. The role of trade unions in defending and demanding both the government and the company they work for, for changes in compensation. According to Budiarti (2008) the role of trade unions is the capability or ability of trade unions to provide protection, defense of rights and interests, settlement of disputes, communication of information, and improving the welfare of workers and their families. According to Huang et al. (2017), trade unions' influence is quite strong; negotiations between trade unions and

companies will influence decisions at the cooperative level. Moreover, according to (Alvita et al., 2014), the role of trade unions is considered good because it has a positive and significant effect on employee welfare. In companies in industrial areas. Other trade unions play a defense role in increasing the income of their members by putting pressure on the government, which in this case has a role in making policies in determining the level of compensation, and the unions also put pressure on companies to always pay attention to the compensation received by employees.

C. Productivity has a significant impact on compensation

Table 3 shows the T-value is $0.69 < 1.96$, which means that the alternative hypothesis (H3) is rejected. The statistical test results show that productivity has no a significant effect on compensation. It means that when working productivity changes, it will not cause significant changes on compensation. It means that when working productivity changes, it will not cause a significant change in compensation. The results of this test show that worker productivity has no significant effect on compensation means that when working productivity changes, it does not cause significant changes to compensation. It shows that if work productivity is high, it does not always affect the level of compensation. It is indeed valid for industrial areas because the government has determined the determination of straightforward compensation through the minimum wage.

D. Wages has a significant impact on compensation

Table 3 shows the T-value is $2.88 > 1.96$, which means that the alternative hypothesis (H4) is accepted. The statistical test results show that wage has a significant effect on compensation. It means that when the wage rate changes, it causes a significant change in compensation. That is, when the wage rate changes, it causes a significant change in compensation. The higher the level of wages received by employees, the compensation will also be more significant because wages are part of compensation, namely financial compensation. The government very dominantly determines wage policy for Indonesia in the form of a regional minimum wage; the determination of this wage level will encourage changes in the overall level of compensation received by employees.

E. Living cost has a significant impact on compensation

Table 3 shows the T-value is $3.01 > 1.96$, which means that the alternative hypothesis (H5) is accepted. The statistical test results show that living cost has a significant effect on compensation. It means that when the living cost changes, it causes a significant change in compensation. That is, when the cost-of-living changes, causing a significant change in compensation. The results of this test show that the cost of living has a significant effect on direct compensation. It means that when the cost-of-living changes, it causes a significant change in the compensation received by employees. According to Sturman et al. (2017), the cost of living has a positive effect on the level of financial compensation, but this only affects the operational level or production level, but for employees at the manager level, this has a less or less positive effect. For this reason, it turns out that the cost of living also dramatically affects the determination of compensation. In industrial companies, the cost of living in some places in Indonesia is considered relatively high, such as housing ownership, that the wages received are not enough to buy a house or a place to live because the price is relatively high, not to mention the cost of food, transportation, and others. Therefore, the cost of living encourages the determination of financial compensation that is even more ideal. Changes in the cost of living due to inflation or an

increase in the price of necessities will be followed by an adjustment of financial compensation based on the inflation rate in the following year, or wages will increase.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out, this research shows that government policies, labor unions, wage levels, and cost of living can affect compensation policy but not productivity which does not affect compensation policy. In addition, compensation policies can mediate all exogenous variables on employee performance, especially for employees who work in the automotive industry in Bekasi, West Java. With the changes in compensation every year, it is better not to hold demonstrations that cost quite a lot, halts some production, and sometimes take casualties. To retain investors, the government should play a significant role in increasing compensation each period while still paying attention to the ability of industrial companies in the Bekasi Regency, West Java, Indonesia. The calculation of the increase in direct compensation should be acceptable to the union as an organization that protects the obligations and rights of its members so that the company can survive.

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